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The Influence of Sharia Income (Murabahah, Mudharabah, Musyarakah) on GWM (Minimum Reserve Requirement) with Firm Size as a Moderation Variable in Islamic Banking in Indonesia Period of 2018-2023

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Abstract

This research analyzes the influence of Murabahah, Mudharabah and Musyarakah Income on the Minimum Reserve Requirement (GWM), with Firm Size as a moderating variable in Islamic banking in Indonesia. Panel data from 5 sharia banks (Bank Muamalat Indonesia, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Bukopin Syariah, BCA Syariah, and Bank Aceh Syariah) for the period 2018.Q1 to 2023.Q3 was processed using panel data regression and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA). The research results show that Murabahah income has a significant positive influence on the Minimum Statutory Reserve, Mudharabah income has no effect on the Minimum Statutory Reserve and Musyarakah income has a negative effect on the Minimum Statutory Reserve. And Murabahah, Mudharabah, & Musyarakah income simultaneously has an influence on GWM. And only 22.67% of the GWM variable can be explained by Murabahah, Mudharabah and Musyarakah income.

Keywords: Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM), Murabahah Income, Mudharabah Income, Musyarakah Income, Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM), Firm Size

INTRODUCTION

Sharia banking is one of the supports for economic growth, including in Indonesia itself, sharia banking has also experienced rapid growth in the last few years. According to data on the Financial Services Authority (OJK) website as of December 2023, there are 14 Sharia Commercial Banks (BUS), 23 Sharia Business Units (UUS), and 166 Sharia People's Financing Banks (BPRS) operating in Indonesia. The combined total assets of sharia banks reached IDR 873.3 trillion. This growth is driven by increasing public awareness of the importance of sharia finance which offers an alternative financial system that is fair and transparent. Sharia banking in building customer loyalty is carried out by applying the Sharia Marketing concept, namely a marketing strategy based on Islamic laws and regulations (Mahfud, 2020) . The following are the four main pillars of Sharia Marketing, among others: Belief in God (Rabbaniyah), Ethical (Akhlaqiah), Realistic (Ala waqi'yyah), and Humanistic (Insyaniah). By implementing Sharia Marketing, Sharia banking can build customer trust and loyalty in a fair, transparent and moral manner, as well as providing benefits for all parties. Apart from that, economic growth is also driven by products that are popular in sharia banking, namely financing products, such as Murabahah, Mudharabah, and Musyarakah. These financing products are one of the sources of profit or income from Islamic banks themselves.

Sharia banks use Murabahah contracts as a result of the community's need for fair and sharia-compliant financing, thereby encouraging the birth of Murabahah schemes. This

scheme is a financing agreement in sharia banking which is based on sharia principles and is regulated in an agreement between the bank and the customer (Basri et al., 2022) . The Murabahah financing flow is where the bank buys goods according to the customer's wishes and then resells them at an agreed profit, and Murabahah is a financing product that can be carried out continuously or in installments (Sindhu & Mubarakah, 2021) . So this Murabahah scheme is a fair and transparent financing scheme that can be a solution to people's financial needs. This scheme offers an alternative funding method that is interest-free and adheres to Islamic principles. Furthermore, Mudharabah Income is income obtained from mudharabah transactions, which is a type of business that involves investment with risks and profits shared between the investor and the company (Latif, 2020) . Musyarakah income is income obtained from Musyarakah transactions, which is a type of business that involves investment with risks and profits shared between the investor and the company (Ichfan & Hasanah, 2021) . Of the various types of sharia banking income, each has different risk and volatility characteristics, so this can affect the bank's ability to meet the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM). Banks are required to set aside a portion of customer funds (DPK) in the form of balances in Bank Indonesia checking accounts. The amount is determined by Bank Indonesia, namely a certain percentage of DPK (Ross et al., 2021) . Moreover, considering the above by considering company size (Firm Size) as a moderating variable, will enable a deeper understanding of the dynamics that exist in the Islamic banking industry in Indonesia. Based on size, companies are categorized into 3 types: large, medium, & small (Jaya, 2020) . Company size is also one of the main considerations for potential investors in deciding to invest their capital. Large companies are generally more attractive to investors because they are considered more stable and have greater profit potential. So if a sharia bank with larger total assets usually has more sources of income and is better able to meet its GWM obligations.

This research uses sharia banking data in Indonesia for the period 2018.Q1-2023.Q3. This data will be used to analyze the influence of income from various types of business on Rupiah GWM (Minimum Reserve Requirement) with Firm Size as a moderating variable. With this research, we will be able to find out the influence of income on Rupiah GWM, as well as the influence of Firm Size on this influence.

THEORITICAL REVIEW

Murabaha Income

Murabahah income is income from buying and selling goods transactions at a price agreed between the bank and the customer, where the bank first purchases the goods and then sells them to the customer at a higher price (Nasution et al., 2022) . Murabahah income is income obtained by the bank through buying and selling transactions between the Bank and customers regarding goods through Murabahah contracts. The price of goods consists of the cost price and previously agreed profit margin. The bank, as a seller, tells the customer the purchase price of goods and then determines the profit (Basri et al., 2022) .

Mudharabah Income

Mudharabah income is income obtained by sharia banks from mudharabah financing, namely a profit sharing agreement between the bank and the customer, where the bank provides capital to the customer for the business, the profits are distributed

based on the agreed ratio. Meanwhile, losses are only borne by the capital owner (Bahri, 2022) . Mudharabah income is income obtained from capital collaboration that benefits both parties, between the capital owner and the capital manager. Capital owners who invest their funds in a business are entitled to the profits obtained from the business. On the other hand, capital managers who run the business are entitled to service fees for their contribution to generating profits. Losses are borne by the capital owner, but if the loss is caused by the manager's negligence, the manager can be held responsible (Satria & Saputri, 2016) .

Musharaka Income

Musyarakah income is income obtained by Islamic banks from musyarakah financing, namely a cooperation agreement between the bank and customers for a business, where profits and losses are shared together according to the agreed distribution of results (Seruni, 2022) . Musyarakah income is income from cooperation agreements formed between banks and customers to help each other in financing a business. The profits and risks obtained from the business will be shared and borne jointly according to the agreement made at the beginning (Satria & Saputri, 2016) . Musyarakah is a cooperative agreement in which two or more parties undertake business activities together. These parties will deposit capital and bear the risks together. The profits obtained from this business will be distributed according to the agreement that has been made (Yuliana & Mubarakah, 2021) .

Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM)

GWM is an obligation for banks to maintain a certain amount of funds in Bank Indonesia. Bank Indonesia determines the amount of GWM as a certain part of the bank's Third Party Funds (DPK) (Gunawan & Barlinti, 2022) . So GWM is a mandatory bank deposit at Bank Indonesia as a liquidity reserve. The amount of GWM is determined by the Central Bank to ensure that the bank has reserve funds to suffice or fulfill all its liquidity obligations, such as customer cash withdrawals, clearing, and others (Elvira et al., 2020) . So GWM helps maintain the stability of banks and the financial system as a whole.

Determination of the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) by Bank Indonesia as a certain percentage of Third Party Funds (DPK) causes an increase in TPF to automatically increase the GWM. In response, Islamic banks utilized income from Murabahah, Mudharabah and Musyarakah products to maintain liquidity and fulfill GWM obligations. This gives rise to a hypothesis, namely:

Murabahah income affects the Minimum Statutory Reserve (H1)

Minimum Statutory Reserve or GWM is the minimum deposit of funds that banks must have in the form of a current account balance kept at Bank Indonesia (BI). Murabahah income is one component of income obtained by sharia banks through buying and selling transactions based on sharia principles. In several previous studies, it was found that GWM and Murabahah Income have a significant relationship with the financial performance of Islamic banks. Several previous studies have found that GWM and Murabahah Income have a significant relationship on the financial performance of Islamic banks. For example, previous research found that GWM has a significant relationship to the financial performance of Islamic banks (Adila, 2022) . Other research

also finds that Murabahah income has a significant relationship to sharia bank income (Rosa & Kusumawaty, 2019) .

Mudharabah income affects the Minimum Statutory Reserve (H2)

Previous research found that DPK, ratio level, and unproductive financing performance have a significant impact on the volume & proportion of profit sharing financing in Islamic banking sector companies in Indonesia (Annisa & Yaya, 2015) . Other research also found that the impact of interest rates on BI & the level of profit sharing for financing at Islamic banks, shows that the level of profit sharing can influence minimum mandatory savings (Iskandar & Adirestuty, 2018) . These studies suggest that income from Mudharabah financing has a positive influence on minimum mandatory savings in sharia banking. Therefore, it is hypothesized that income from Mudharabah financing has a positive influence or impact on GWM.

Musyarakah income affects the Minimum Statutory Reserve (H3)

Musyarakah income has the potential to influence the Statutory Minimum Reserve. In a Musyarakah contract, the bank and customer participate in joint business management with joint capital and profit sharing according to the agreement. In collaborating with GWM, banks have the opportunity to increase income through increasing interest rates on third party funds. GWM, one of the bank's strategies to increase income by increasing the interest rate on GWM third party funds. Bank Indonesia requires banks to have minimum statutory reserves (GWM) in two types, namely rupiah and foreign currency. Other research results state that the existence of the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) has a positive impact on financing in the form of PT credit. Bank Central Asia, Tbk. Indonesia during the 2001-2015 period (Fitri, 2017) . Apart from that, other research also found that GWM implemented a strategy of increasing interest rates on savings products such as savings and deposits to attract people's interest in putting their money in banks. This resulted in an increase in third party funds collected by GWM, thereby increasing its funding (Pradhana, 2016) .

Firm Size

Size is a reflection of the level of public trust in the company that was formed over a certain period of time, generally from its founding until now. This trust is built through various processes of company activities and performance (Indrayani et al., 2021) . Meanwhile, according to another opinion, firm size indicates the size of its assets and attracts investor interest because it indicates stability and growth potential (Sari & Wiyanto, 2022) .

Company size (Firm Size) in this study is used as a form of moderating variable. This aims to understand how other factors, such as operating scale, influence the relationship between sharia financial product income & Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM. Based on Firm Size moderation, this research tests the following three hypotheses:

Firm Size has a moderating effect on the relationship between Murabahah Income & Minimum Statutory Reserves (GWM (H4)

Sharia banks with a larger Firm Size generally have broad & high operational efficiency. This allows them to manage GWM more efficiently & earn higher murabahah

income. Previous research analyzed the influence of company size (Firm Size), Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM), and the environment on the profitability of sharia companies. It was found that although this research did not directly test Firm Size as a moderating variable, it was found that Firm Size had a significant impact on the profitability of sharia companies (Shafryani, 2022) .

Firm Size has a moderating effect on the relationship between Mudharabah Income & Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) (H5)

Sharia banks with a larger Firm Size generally have high operational efficiency. This allows banks to manage GWM more efficiently and generate higher Mudharabah Income. Previous research suggests that although firm size was not tested directly as a moderating variable in previous research, financial ratios have been proven to have an influence on banking profitability. This influence can vary, depending on the type of financial ratio used (Shafiin, 2023) . Research by Mansur, et al (2020) suggests that the impact of company size on profitability is by considering the role of corporate governance as a moderating variable. Even though it is not in the context of Islamic banking, it can provide an idea of how other factors can moderate the relationship between company size and financial performance.

Firm Size has a moderating effect on the relationship between Musyarakah Income & Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) (H6)

Islamic banks with a larger Firm Size generally have higher operational efficiency. This allows banks to manage GWM more efficiently and generate higher Musyarakah Income. Previous research examined the influence of GWM & DPK on the level of musyarakah financing at Bank Mega Syariah. Even though it does not link Firm Size as a moderating variable, this research shows that GWM influences the level of musyarakah financing at Bank Mega Syariah (Randa, 2023) .

Murabahah Income, Mudharabah Income, and Musyarakah Income influence the Statutory Reserve (GWM) (H7)

The following are dependent variables that are influenced by independent variables, as explained in the Concept Map below:

Figure

1.

Concept Map

Source: Author (2024)

METHOD

The method used in this research is a quantitative method. Secondary data used in this research is from Islamic banking financial reports in Indonesia for the period 2018.Q1 to 2023.Q3. This research data comes from financial reports & annual reports downloaded from Islamic banking websites. The sampling technique used was Purposive Sampling. The sample used was 5 Sharia Banks during 2018.Q1 to 2023.Q3, so the total sample was 115 Sharia bank statistics from quarterly financial reports in 2018-2023.

In this research, the author used 2 data analysis methods, including the Panel Data Regression Model & Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA). Ghozali (2018) stated that MRA, also known as Interaction Test, allows researchers to study the influence of moderator variables (factors that modify the relationship between two variables) without having to sacrifice data samples. The following regression model is applied in panel data analysis:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + e_i$$

Where:

Y = Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM)

α = Constant

β = Regression Coefficient

X1 = Murabahah income

X2 = Mudharabah Income

X3 = Musharaka Income

e_i = Error

Hypothesis testing in this study uses regression analysis with a moderating variable, namely MRA, which has similarities to regression which includes interaction elements with the following formula:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_5X_1*Z + \beta_6X_2*Z + \beta_7X_3*Z + e_i$$

Where:

Y = Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM)

α = Constant

β = Regression Coefficient

X1 = Murabahah Income

X2 = Mudharabah income

X3 = Musharaka Income

X_1*Z = Multiplicative interaction between Murabahah Income and Firm Size

X_2*Z = Multiplicative interaction between Mudharabah Income and Firm Size

X_3*Z = Multiplicative interaction between Musyarakah Income and Firm Size

e_i = Error.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Descriptive analysis

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

	X1	X2	X3	Y	Z
Mean	1074393.	28360.33	524801.7	5.196348	17.00652
Maximum	11354171	221513.0	4722223.	10.88000	19.58000
Minimum	13891.00	0.000000	23919.00	0.000000	15.45000
Std. Dev.	2067375.	37135.26	875018.6	1.750821	1.150835
Observations	115	115	115	115	115

Reference: Data processed by the author using Eviews 12 Software

According to Table 1, Table 1 shows that this research involved 115 samples from sharia banking in Indonesia, collected from their financial reports for the period 2018.Q1 to 2023.Q3. Descriptive analysis of the Murabahah Income variable (X1) in Table 1 reveals that the average value of this variable is 1074393, with a maximum value of 11354171, a minimum value of 13891.00, & a std deviation of 2067375.

Analysis of table 1 shows that the average Mudharabah Income variable (X2) is 28360.33. The highest value is 221513.0, the lowest is 0.000000, and the standard deviation is 37135.26

Analysis of the Musyarakah Income variable (X3) shows that the average Musyarakah income is 524801.7 with the highest value reaching 4722223. and the lowest value 23919.00. The standard deviation is 875018.6

Based on table 1, descriptive analysis shows that the average Minimum Statutory Reserve (Y) is 5.196348, with the highest value being 10.88000 and the lowest being 0.000000. The standard deviation is 1.750821.

Based on table 1, descriptive statistical analysis shows that the Company Value (Firm Size) variable has an average of 17.00652, a maximum value of 19.58000, a minimum value of 15.45000, & a std deviation of 1.150835.

Determination of the regression model on panel data

Selection of regression models on panel data is an analysis stage to determine the best method between Fixed Effect Model (FEM), Common Effect Model (CEM), & Random Effects Model (REM).

Test Chow

The Chow test was carried out to see the best model between the CEM & FEM models.

Table 2. Chow Test Results

Effects Test	Statistics	df	Prob.
Cross-section F	1.107984	(4,107)	0.3567
Chi-square cross-section	4.667290	4	0.3232

Reference: Data processed by the author using Eviews 12 Software

Based on the analysis of Table 2, the results of the Chow Test analysis show that the Cross-Sectionchi-Square probability value is 0.3232, which is more than 0.05. This test shows that the most appropriate model to implement is the Common Effect Model

(CEM).

Lagrange Multiplier Test

Lagrange Multiplier test is used to test the Random Effect Model (REM) which is based on the residual values from the Common Effect Model (CEM).

Table 3. Lagrange Multiplier Results

	Test Hypothesis		
	Cross-section	Time	Both
Breusch-Pagan	0.440967	85.83430	86.27527
	(0.5067)	(0.0000)	(0.0000)

Reference: Data processed by the author using Eviews 12 Software

Based on table 4, the results of the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) Test show that the possibility that CEM is more appropriate to use is large. This is because the probability value (p-value) is 0.5067, which is greater than the standard reference value of 0.05, which is the commonly used statistical significance limit. Therefore, in this test, the most appropriate model to use is the Common Effect Model (CEM).

Test classical assumptions

Normality Test

Table 4. Normality Test

Reference: Data processed by the author using Eviews 12 Software

The results of the analysis in table 4, the analysis shows that the probability level reaches 0.762224, a figure that exceeds the significance limit of 0.05 (0.762224 > 0.05). Thus, it can be concluded that the data in this study has a high probability of following a normal distribution.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test

	LOG(X1)	X2	X3
LOG(1)	1,000000	0.535391	0.659243
X2	0.535391	1,000000	0.787687
X3	0.659243	0.787687	1,000000

Reference: Data processed by the author using Eviews 12 Software

Analysis of table 5 shows that the relationship between independent variables is classified as weak, with a correlation value below 0.85. This indicates that there is no multicollinearity in the research data, so that a regression model is obtained that is free from distortion due to independent variables influencing each other.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 6. Heteroscedasticity Test

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
X1	-1.65E-07	1.70E-07	-0.969842	0.3343
X2	-1.82E-06	4.45E-06	-0.408899	0.6834
X3	3.02E-07	4.50E-07	0.671602	0.5033
C	-1.208054	2.007618	-0.601735	0.5486

Source: Data processed by the author using Eviews 12 Software

Data analysis in Table 6 shows that the possibility of heteroscedasticity in this regression model is relatively low. This is proven by a probability value greater than 0.05. These findings support the research conclusion that the regression model used is free from heteroscedasticity problems.

Regression Analysis of P anel Data

The following is the Best Approach, namely Panel Data Regression Analysis with CEM :

Table 7. Common Effect Model panel data regression analysis

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	5.214283	0.201896	25.82659	0.0000
X1	4.27E-07	2.77E-07	1.542097	0.1259
X2	-1.02E-05	7.23E-06	-1.409561	0.1615
X3	-3.58E-07	7.46E-07	-0.479260	0.6327

Reference: Data processed by the author using Eviews 12 Software

Moderated regression analysis (Moderated Regression Analysis-MRA)

Moderation regression analysis has been carried out to test the effect of moderating variables on the relationship between independent & dependent variables. The results of the analysis show that moderating variables can strengthen or weaken this relationship.

Table 8. Moderation Regression Analysis Test

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	5.301602	0.335966	15.78018	0.0000
X1	6.71E-06	6.29E-06	1.067186	0.2883

X2	4.94E-05	0.000119	0.414992	0.6790
X3	-2.12E-05	1.84E-05	-1.149557	0.2529
X1Z	-3.64E-07	3.62E-07	-1.006133	0.3166
X2Z	-3.12E-06	6.50E-06	-0.480785	0.6316
X3Z	1.17E-06	1.03E-06	1.129597	0.2611

Reference: Data processed by the author using Eviews 12 Software

Statistical test

T test

The t test is a statistical tool used to assess whether the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable is strong enough to be said to be significant. In other words, the t test helps us determine whether the independent variable has a real effect on the dependent variable. This test is carried out by setting a confidence level of 95%, which means we are 95% sure that the results obtained are correct. On the other hand, an error rate of 5% indicates that there is a 5% risk that the results obtained will be incorrect.

Table 9. T test

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	5.301602	0.335966	15.78018	0.0000
X1	6.71E-06	6.29E-06	1.067186	0.2883
X2	4.94E-05	0.000119	0.414992	0.6790
X3	-2.12E-05	1.84E-05	-1.149557	0.2529
X1Z	-3.64E-07	3.62E-07	-1.006133	0.3166
X2Z	-3.12E-06	6.50E-06	-0.480785	0.6316
X3Z	1.17E-06	1.03E-06	1.129597	0.2611

Reference: Data processed by the author using Eviews 12 Software

According to the results of the T Test (partial) in this research, it can be concluded that the results obtained from the T Test are as follows:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Effect of Murabahah Income on the Statutory Minimum Reserve (GWM). The analysis shows that the coefficient value for the Murabahah Income variable (X1) is 6.71E-06 and the probability value is 0.2883, meaning that the value obtained is less than the significance value of 0.5 or 5%. So this states that Murabahah Income has the ability to significantly influence the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) in Islamic banking sector companies in Indonesia in the period 2018.Q1-2023.Q3.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Effect of Mudharabah Income on Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM). The analysis shows that the coefficient value for the Mudharabah Income variable (X2) is 4.94E-05 and the probability value is 0.6790, meaning that the value obtained is greater than the significance value of 0.5 or 5%. So this states that Mudharabah Income is unable to influence the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) in Islamic banking sector companies in Indonesia in the period 2018.Q1-2023.Q3.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): The influence of Musyarakah Income on the Statutory Minimum Reserve (GWM). The analysis shows that the coefficient value for the Musyarakah Income variable (X3) is -2.12E-05 and the Probability value is 0.2529, meaning that the value obtained is less than the significance value of 0.5 or 5%. So this states that

Musyarakah Income has the ability to significantly influence GWM in Islamic banking sector companies in Indonesia in the period 2018.Q1-2023.Q3.

Hypothesis 4 (H4): Firm Size has a moderating effect on the relationship between Murabahah Income & Minimum Statutory Reserves (GWM). The analysis shows a coefficient number of $-3.64E-07$ and a probability value of 0.3166, meaning the value obtained is less than 0.5 significance or 5%. So this states that Firm Size is able to moderate the relationship between Murabahah Income and GWM in Islamic banking sector companies in Indonesia in the period 2018.Q1-2023.Q3.

Hypothesis 5 (H5): Firm Size has a moderating effect on the relationship between Mudharabah Income & Minimum Statutory Reserves (GWM). The analysis shows a coefficient number of $-3.12E-06$ and a probability value of 0.6316, meaning the value obtained is greater than the significance value of 0.5 or 5%. So this states that Firm Size is unable to moderate the relationship between Mudharabah Income and GWM in Islamic banking sector companies in Indonesia in the period 2018.Q1-2023.Q3.

Hypothesis 6 (H6): Firm Size has a moderating effect on the relationship between Musharakah Income & Minimum Statutory Reserves (GWM). The analysis shows a coefficient value of $1.17E-06$ and a probability value of 0.2611, meaning the value obtained is less than the significance value of 0.5 or 5%. So this states that Firm Size is able to moderate the relationship between Musyarakah Income and GWM in Islamic banking sector companies in Indonesia in the period 2018.Q1-2023.Q3.

F test

The F test is used to test whether the independent variables simultaneously have a significant influence on the dependent variable.

Table 10. F test

Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000
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Reference: Data processed by the author using Eviews 12 Software

This research uses the F test with a significance level of 5% or 0.05. This means that if the F significance value is smaller than 0.05, then the regression coefficient is considered valid. Based on the F Test results in Table 10, the significance value of F is 0.000000, meaning it is greater than 0.05. So, it can be concluded that Murabahah Income, Mudharabah Income and Musyarakah Income have an important influence on the Statutory Minimum Reserve (GWM).

Coefficient of Determination Test

The Coefficient of Determination value helps understand how much variation in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables in the regression model.

Table 11. Determination Coefficient Test

Adjusted R-squared	0.226789
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Reference: Data processed by the author using Eviews 12 Software

According to Table 11, the panel data regression test results for the dependent variable Statutory Reserves show a value of Adjusted R-squared of 0.226789. This means that 22.67% of the Statutory Minimum Reserve can be explained by Murabahah Income, Mudharabah Income and Musyarakah Income, while the remainder is explained by other variables outside the regression model.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Murabahah Income on the Statutory Minimum Reserve

The T Test shows that the Probability of Murabahah Income value is 0.2883, namely <0.05 . This test also shows a positive direction with a coefficient value of 6.71E-06, t-Statistic 1.067186, and so it can be concluded that Murabahah Income has a positive effect on the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) in Islamic banking sector companies in Indonesia in the period 2018.Q1-2023.Q3. Therefore, the hypothesis proposed by the researcher, namely H1: Murabahah income has an effect on the Statutory Minimum Reserve, is accepted.

This test is in line with previous research by Adila (2022) , Rosa & Kusumawaty (2019) which stated that GWM and Murabahah Income have a significant relationship on the financial performance of Islamic banks. Other research also found that Murabahah, Mudharabah, and Musyarakah financing had a positive and significant effect on profitability levels (Pratama et al., 2017) .

The Effect of Mudharabah Income on the Statutory Minimum Reserve

The T Test shows that the Mudharabah Income Probability value is 0.6790, namely >0.05 . This test also shows a positive direction with a coefficient value of 4.94E-05, t-Statistic 0.414992, and it is concluded that Mudharabah Income has no effect on GWM in Islamic banking sector companies in Indonesia in the period 2018.Q1-2023.Q3. Therefore, the hypothesis proposed by the researcher, namely H2: The Effect of Mudharabah Income on the Statutory Minimum Reserve not accepted.

In this test, new findings were found that mudharabah income was not able to influence the GWM, and this is different from existing research, for example by Annisa & Yaya (2015) who in his research found that TPF, the ratio level, and the performance of unproductive financing have a significant impact on the volume & proportion of profit-sharing financing in sharia banking in Indonesia. Other research by Iskandar & Adirestuty (2018) also found that the impact of interest rates on BI & the rate of profit sharing for financing at Islamic banks, shows that the level of profit sharing can influence minimum mandatory savings.

The Influence of Musyarakah Income on the Statutory Minimum Reserve

The T Test shows that the Probability of Musyarakah Income value is 0.2529, namely <0.05 . This test also shows a negative direction with a coefficient value of -2.12E-05, t-Statistic -1.149557, and it is concluded that Musyarakah Income has a negative effect on GWM in Islamic banking sector companies in Indonesia in the period 2018.Q1-2023.Q3. Therefore, the hypothesis proposed by researchers, namely H3: The Effect of Musyarakah Income on Minimum Statutory Reserves is accepted.

This test is in line with previous research by the results of other research by Irwansyah & Hidayat (2021) which found that the murabahah and mudharabah

financing variables of Sharia Commercial Banks simultaneously significantly influence the ROA variable of Sharia Commercial Banks. Apart from that, other research states that the existence of GWM has a positive impact on credit distribution by PT. Bank Central Asia, Tbk. in Indonesia during the 2001-2015 period (Fitri, 2017). Apart from that, other research also found that GWM implemented a strategy of increasing interest rates on savings products such as savings and deposits to attract people's interest in putting their money in banks. This resulted in an increase in third party funds collected by GWM, thereby increasing its funding (Pradhana, 2016).

Firm Size moderates the relationship between Murabahah Income and Statutory Reserves

In the T test, it shows a probability value of 0.3166, namely <0.05 . This test also shows a negative direction with a coefficient value of $-3.64E-07$, t-Statistic -1.006133 , and it is concluded that Firm Size can strengthen the relationship between Murabahah Income and Minimum Statutory Reserves (GWM) in Islamic banking sector companies in Indonesia in the 2018 period..Q1-2023.Q3. Therefore, the hypothesis proposed by researchers, namely H4: Firm Size moderates the relationship between Murabahah Income and Minimum Statutory Reserves, is accepted.

This test is in line with previous research which analyzed the influence of company size (Firm Size), Minimum Statutory Reserves (GWM), and the environment on the profitability of sharia companies. It was found that although this research did not directly test Firm Size as a moderating variable, it was found that Firm Size had a significant impact on the profitability of sharia companies (Shafryani, 2022) .

Firm Size moderates the relationship between Mudharabah Income and Statutory Minimum Reserves

In the T Test, it shows a probability value of 0.6316, namely >0.05 . This test also shows a negative direction with a coefficient value of $-3.12E-06$, t-Statistic -0.480785 , and so it can be concluded that Firm Size cannot strengthen the relationship between Mudharabah Income and GWM in Islamic banking sector companies in Indonesia in the 2018 period.Q1 -2023.Q3. Therefore, the hypothesis proposed by researchers, namely H5: Firm Size moderates the relationship between Mudharabah Income and Minimum Statutory Reserves, is rejected.

This test shows new findings because it is different from previous research which stated that although this research did not directly test Firm Size as a moderate variable, financial ratios have an influence on banking profitability, both a significant influence and also a positive influence or a negative influence, depending on the type of ratio. his finances (Shafiin, 2023) . Research by Mansur, et al (2020) suggests that the impact of company size on profitability is by considering the role of corporate governance as a moderating variable. Even though it is not in the context of Islamic banking, it can provide an idea of how other factors can moderate the relationship between company size and financial performance.

Firm Size moderates the relationship between Musyarakah Income and Statutory Reserves

In the T test, it shows a probability value of 0.2611, namely <0.05 . This test also shows a positive direction with a coefficient value of $1.17E-06$, t-Statistic 1.129597 , and

so it can be concluded that Firm Size can strengthen the relationship between Musharaka Income and GWM in Islamic banking sector companies in Indonesia in the period 2018.Q1-2023.Q3. Therefore, the hypothesis proposed by researchers, namely H6: Firm Size moderates the relationship between Musharaka Income and Minimum Statutory Reserves, is accepted.

This test is in line with previous research by Randa (2023) which examined the influence of GWM & DPK on the level of musyarakah financing at Bank Mega Syariah. Even though it does not link Firm Size as a moderating variable, this research shows that GWM has an effect on the level of musharaka financing at Bank Mega Syariah.

Effect of Murabahah Income, Mudharabah Income, & Musyarakah Income Simultaneously on Statutory Minimum Reserves

Based on the results of the F Test that has been carried out, it can be concluded that simultaneously, murabahah, mudharabah and musyarakah income have a significant effect on GWM. This is because the significance value of 0.000000 is smaller than 0.05. Therefore, the three independent variables (Murabahah, Mudharabah, and Musyarakah income) simultaneously influence the GWM. So it can be concluded that the hypothesis proposed by the researcher, namely H7: The effect of Murabahah Income, Mudharabah Income, & Musyarakah Income simultaneously on the Minimum Statutory Reserve is accepted.

Apart from that, the Determination Test that was carried out resulted in an Adjusted R-squared value of 0.226789. So this value shows that these three variables contribute an influence on GWM of 22.67% and the remaining 77.33% is influenced by other factors, therefore to carry out this research you can use other independent variables.

CONCLUSION

The results of this research indicate that Murabahah income shows a significant positive influence on the Minimum Statutory Reserve, which means that the higher the murabahah income, the higher the GWM of sharia banks. This shows that murabahah products play an important role in increasing the liquidity of Islamic banks. Mudharabah Income has no effect on the Statutory Minimum Reserve, meaning, no clear relationship is found between mudharabah income and Islamic bank GWM. This could be because the characteristics of mudharabah products are different from murabahah, where mudharabah focuses more on profit sharing. Musharaka Income has a negative effect on the Minimum Statutory Reserve, meaning that the higher the musyarakah income, the lower the GWM of sharia banks. This could be because musharaka capital originating from banks and customers is managed together for business, so that the funds available for GWM are reduced. Bank size (Firm Size) also has the ability to strengthen the influence of Murabahah and Musyarakah income on GWM, but does not have the ability to strengthen the influence of Mudharabah income on GWM. And Murabahah, Mudharabah, & Musyarakah income simultaneously has an influence on GWM. And only 22.67% of the GWM variable can be explained by Murabahah, Mudharabah and Musyarakah income.

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